

DUCTILITY OF PLATELET COMPOSITES INSPIRED BY NACRE DESIGN

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ABSTRACT

Platelet composite design inspired by nacre microstructure has attracted wide interest as a means to improving toughness of materials. Presented within this paper are novel approaches in to engendering simultaneous improvements to the pseudo ductility and strength improvement simultaneously in discontinuous fibre reinforced epoxy composites. The approaches were finger type ply overlapping, discontinuous platelets and z-pin reinforcement of joints. A comparative numerical and experimental study is described in this paper to identify the relationship between ply-overlap length and strain ductility of a platelet composite design with z-pin reinforcement. Larger-The results show that a carbon fibre epoxy platelet composite ply overlap length is can found to retain 45% and 93%, respectively, of the tensile strength and failure strain of the continuous fibre composite counterpart. A relatively small pseudo-ductility strain of 1.07% was observed. Analytical modelling studies towards these were conducted on platelet or discontinuous fibre reinforced epoxy composites with of platelet composites of varying aspect ratios and tiling configurations. Results suggest that the staggering of the neighbouring ply terminations resulted in an increased tensile strength whereas aligning the ply-termination for each second consecutive ply leads to the increase in strain-to-failure. The incorporation of z-pin reinforcements (stainless steel, copper and carbon fibre/BMI) through-the-thickness of the platelet composite was investigated. The shear-induced work hardening of the metal pins further enhances the pseudo-ductile strain and strength simultaneously; supplementing the shear lag process between the ply-overlaps.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Discontinuous fibre reinforced polymer composites ~~such as made of~~ chopped strand mats [1], unidirectionally arrayed chopped strands (UACS) [2], ~~or and~~ platelet composite structures [3], ~~are desired due to offer improved the ease of~~ processability and drapability ~~when compared to continuous fibre manufacturing advanced lightweight structures~~. However, a major drawback of discontinuous fibre reinforced epoxy composites are the relatively low mechanical properties compared to composites containing their continuous fibre counterparts [1-3]. More importantly, the linear elastic stress-strain behaviour both discontinuous and continuous fibre composites often results in an have inherently inherent low lack of ductility and under tensile loading conditions and can rupture fail catastrophically at low strain [1-3]. Hence, there is a desire ~~for to~~ engender more graceful (progressive plastic) failure modes and higher failure strain in fibre reinforced epoxy platelet composites used within the industry.

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High strain ductility is a major requirement in civil and aerospace applications of fibre reinforced polymer composites. Recently significant research has focused on ways to impart ductility or pseudo-ductility to laminated carbon fibre reinforced epoxy composites. Current methods include the incorporation of cross-ply or angled-ply layup configurations whereby the shear-induced rotation of the angled fibres induces creates a large strain prior to rupture [4]. Another popular effective technique is hybridization or intermingling of a ductile reinforcement phase such as a metal, glass fibre or polymer reinforcements [5- & -6], resulting in a non-linear stress-strain response. Some n On the other hand, natural composites, structures such as nacre, contain an alternating, staggered and overlapping network of brittle constituents (i.e. platelets) [7]. Nacre, when subjected to a tensile load, tend to exhibit a progressive failure mode whilst simultaneously exhibiting a greater strength with increasing strain [7]. These are often dominated by the extrinsic and intrinsic toughening process that occur between the interfaces of the platelet overlaps [7]. Czel et al. [8] demonstrated that a pseudo-ductile strain response could be achieved in unidirectional discontinuous carbon fibre/epoxy prepreg composite containing a half-tile offset joint configuration, where the ply gaps were aligned for every second ply, consecutively. However, it is not clear how the staggering of the ply terminations and changes in the mode II interlaminar fracture toughness affect the ductility of platelet composites.

The present paper describes a study on the effect of ply overlap length and z-pins on the quasi-static tensile stress-strain response of platelet composites. Firstly a systematic experimental and finite element analysis was first conducted, followed by ~~Secondly~~ a numerical investigation on the effect of tilting configuration and the mode II interlaminar fracture energy on the strength and ductility of the representative of a unidirectional platelet composite containing sixteen plies. Finally, an experimental investigation is was conducted by inserting micron diameter scale metal and composite rods, or z-pins to through the ~~the~~ thickness of platelet composite, mimicking the mineral bridging and in-elastic shearing between the platelets of nacreous structures.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Materials and specimen configuration Experimental details

The co-cured composite joints used in this study were made of using a Unidirectional T700 carbon fibre-epoxy prepreg tape (VTM 264 supplied by Lavender Composites) was selected to manufacture continuous and platelet fibre reinforced polymer composites. ~~For the first comparative experimental and numerical modelling study, as~~ The specimen design and test fixture are shown in Fig. 1a. The specimens, similar to a finger joint, consisted of the four-ply half tile offset joints contained a stacking sequence of [0]₄ laminates with ply overlap lengths between 10 mm and to 80 mm. These

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four ply finger joints were cut into 20 mm wide, 0.9 mm thick and 220 mm long samples, with containing 50 mm long glass fibre tabs on the ends. The width, thickness, and length of the specimens are 20 mm, 0.9 mm, and 220 mm. Glass fibre composite tabs (50 mm in length) were attached on the ends. In assessing the of-effects of z-pins-type (i.e., third study) ontowards on the mechanical properties of the-butted double lap joints, three different types of the-z-pins,-that were used included 0.5 mm in diameter, were used: carbon fibre/BMI, stainless steel (316L), and copper (99.9% purity) pins rods with a volume fraction of content of 2.0 vol%. Schematic of the joint-z-pinned lap joint configuration is shown in Fig-1b. The z-pinned composite joint contained a ply stacking sequence of [0/90]₇, that were cut into 25 mm wide, 610 mm thick and 145 mm long samples-containing a 50 mm long glass fibre tabs on the ends. Glass fibre composite tabs (50 mm in length) were attached on the ends for testing. The carbon fibre/ BMI z-pins (Albany Engineered Composite Pty Ltd.) were inserted through-the-thickness of the ply overlapped region of the joint using the ultrasonically-assisted pinning (UAZ) process [9]. As described in [9], the copper and stainless steel z-pins were inserted using a template-template-assisted approach. For the first and third study, quasi-static tensile tests were conducted using a 100 kN MTS and a 50 kN Instron Universal-universal Testing-testing Machine machine-for the first and third study, respectively, at a loading rate of 1.0 mm/min. The gauge region of the samples was coated with a white paint along with a black speckle pattern for *in-situ* strain measurement via digital image correlation (DIC) when-during tensile testing.

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2.2 Computational mModelling approach

The continuous fibre and platelet composite laminates were modelled using ABAQUS CAE 6.14 to predict the in-plane tensile stress-strain versus behaviour of four-ply half-tile offset joints and sixteen-ply, [0]₁₆, platelet composite containing a unidirectional layup. In relation toAs indicated by the schematics depicted on-in Fig.-1a, 1c and 1d-and Fig.-2, the individual plies were modelled using continuum shell elements (SC8R); where the interfaces between the carbon-carbon-ply overlaps were modelled using cohesive elements (COH3D8). Fibre and matrix damage were modelled using the continuum damage mechanical (CDM) approach with the Hashin criterion described in [10]. Cohesive zone modelling (CZM) was incorporated-used to model the delamination cracking between the ply-overlaps. The parameters used for the modelling studies are listed in Table 1. Through a mesh refinement study, the optimal element length and width was computed to be 0.2 mm. These techniques were incorporated into the first and second study.

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For the platelet composites, two configurations were considered: (a) ordered discontinuous and (b) staggered discontinuous tiling configuration, as shown in Fig.-1c and Fig.-1d2b, respectively. Ordered discontinuous tiling configuration contains a ply overlap length that is half of the platelet length. The staggered discontinuous tiling configuration containing-contains a ply overlap length that is 40% of the platelet length. Demonstrated in Fig.-2b, this was conducted to stagger the ply gaps for every four consecutive plies. In replicating the quasi-static tensile loading conditions, numerical analysis was carried out using ABAQUS/Implicit solver at-in displacement control.

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Figure 1: (a) image of the failure mode of the unidirectional four-ply half-tile offset joint. (b) Double lap butted joint configuration containing z-pin reinforcements. (c) Representative volume of unidirectional platelet composite architecture containing (c) ordered discontinuous and (d) staggered discontinuous ply terminations. (Note: the length of the representative volume of the platelet composites is the sum of three platelet length plus a 20 mm excess gauge region on each end.)

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T700/VTM264		
Parameters (Units)	Value	Source
Longitudinal tensile strength, $X_{11,t}$ (MPa)	2500	[10]
Input Longitudinal compressive strength, $X_{11,c}$ (MPa)	1235	[10]
Transverse tensile strength, $Y_{22,t}$ (MPa)	40	[10]
Transverse compressive strength, $Y_{22,c}$ (MPa)	182	[10]
Longitudinal shear strength, $S_{12,t}$ (MPa)	85.7	[10]
Longitudinal tensile fracture toughness, G_{ft} (kJ/m ²)	70	[10]
Longitudinal compressive fracture toughness, G_{fc} (kJ/m ²)	78	[10]
Transverse tensile fracture toughness, G_{mt} (kJ/m ²)	0.3	[10]
Transverse compressive fracture toughness, G_{mc} (kJ/m ²)	0.76	[10]
Interlaminar peel strength, S_{33} (MPa)	40	[10]
Interlaminar shear strength, S_{13} (MPa)	77	[10]
Interlaminar shear strength, S_{33} (MPa)	77	[10]
Mode I fracture toughness, G_{Ic} (kJ/m ²)	0.3	[10]
Mode II fracture toughness, G_{IIc} (kJ/m ²)	1.1	[11]
Mode III fracture toughness, G_{IIIc} (kJ/m ²)	1.1	Assume $G_{IIc} = G_{IIIc}$
Cohesive stiffness, K_I, K_{II} and K_{III} (N/mm ³)	1×10^6	[10]

Table 1: Parameters used for the numerical modelling study.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Experimental vs. numerical modelling results of four-ply half-tile offset joints

Fig.-2a, 2b and 2c present a comparison of the experimental and numerical modelling results of the four ply half-tile offset joint design depicting showing the in-plane stress-strain behaviour, ultimate tensile strength and peak tensile strain, respectively, as a function of the ply overlap length. Numerical modelling results are in good agreement with the experimental results within ~95%, indicating that the combined CDM and CZM approach captures the damage mechanisms of ply rupture and delamination along the interfaces between the ply overlaps. As shown in Fig.-2a, the stress-strain curve rises linearly to a peak in-plane tensile stress of ~1100MPa. For the joint containing the 30 mm overlap length, this was followed by a non-linear pseudo-ductile strain of ~0.15% above which where the joint failed along the co-cured interface. Depicted Shown in Fig.-2b and 2c, a strength retention of 110 MPa and a pseudo-ductile strain of 1.07% were achieved when the ply overlap length exceeded 80 mm.

Figure 2: Comparison of experimental and numerical modelling results of 4 ply half-tile offset unidirectional joint showing (a) stress versus strain curve of joint with a 30 mm ply overlap length, (b) ultimate tensile strength and (c) peak tensile strain as a function of the ply overlap length

During loading, the pseudo-ductile strain observed was induced by a result of the shear-lag between the ply-overlaps as delamination crack growth occurred along the bond-line. Previously it has been shown, that a longer ply overlap length with similar joint configuration reported within this study does promote a pseudo ductile strain response due to the transitioning of the bond line wherewith crack growth crack-transitioning from an unstable to stable crack propagation mode [8]. The progressive crack growth along the ply interface slightly increases the in-plane shear load transfer between the

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~~adherends~~sublaminates. The in-plane tensile strength of the joint for short ply overlap lengths is influenced by the interlaminar shear strength, whereas at large overlap length the in-plane tensile strength is dominated by the interlaminar mode II fracture toughness- [5 & 10].

3.2 Effect of tiling configuration on quasi-static tensile properties of unidirectional platelet composites

Fig.-3a, 3b and 3c present the in-plane stress-strain ~~behaviour~~curves, ultimate tensile strength and ~~peak~~-maximum tensile strain of the unidirectional ordered and staggered discontinuous platelet composite as a function of the ply overlap length. -As shown in Fig.-3a, where ~~by~~ the ply overlap length is ~~approximately~~ 80 mm, ~~it well noted that the~~ ~~representative sixteen-sixteen-ply configuration~~ ~~platelet model~~ with a staggered discontinuous platelet architecture exhibited a much greater retention of the ultimate tensile strength ~~as opposed to~~ ~~than~~ the model containing the ordered discontinuous platelet architecture. The increase in the ultimate tensile strength is further ~~emphasised~~ ~~illustrated~~ in Fig.-3b, with the increase in ply overlap length. Baucom et al. [3] and Ahamed et al. [10] demonstrated that offsetting the ply gap along the thickness of a fibre reinforced polymer composite laminate does lead a greater retention in the ultimate tensile strength ~~and often considered when designing bonded composite structures.~~ ~~During tensile loading, the stress concentration or accumulation surrounding the plies at the ply gap is far less for the staggered discontinuous platelet configuration.~~ ~~During tensile loading, the stress concentration level near ply gaps in the staggered discontinuous platelet configuration is far less than those pertaining to the ordered discontinuous composite, due to the non-alignment of the ply terminations.~~ Nacreous structures such as abalone shell do indeed exhibit this type of platelet architecture, ~~;~~ leading to a greater ~~exhibition of~~ strength and, most importantly, ductility [7, ~~&~~ 12].

It is interesting to note, however, that the strain-to-failure of the ordered discontinuous platelet composite is greater than that of the staggered discontinuous platelet composite with increasing length, as shown in Fig.-3c. The stress-strain response of the ordered platelet composite is more linear than that of the staggered counterpart.

Numerical modelling of the influence of the interlaminar mode II fracture toughness (G_{IIc}) on the strength and ductility of staggered discontinuous platelet composite showed that residual ultimate tensile strength increased with an increasing G_{IIc} till 2.0kJ/m^2 as shown in Fig.-3d. The dominant failure mode of the discontinuous composites described within the *Section 3.1 and 3.2* of this paper is the progressive interlaminar delamination between the plies. Increasing the G_{IIc} results in higher load to propagate the delamination. Nacre uses multiple toughening mechanisms at multiple length scales to enhance progressive failure and to increase the tensile strength. Established techniques for improving the G_{IIc} range from 3D fibre reinforced binders [13] to discrete through-the-thickness reinforcement such as z-pins [9, 11 & 13].

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Figure 3: Comparison of numerical modelling results of 16 ply platelet composite depicting showing (a) stress versus strain curve of joints containing an 80 mm ply overlap length, (b) ultimate tensile strength and (c) peak tensile strain as a function of the ply overlap length. Effect of mode II interlaminar fracture toughness on the stress versus strain behaviour of the discontinuous composite with a ply overlap length of 80mm.

3.3 Effect of z-pin type on quasi-static tensile properties of butted double lap joints

Fig. 4a presents shows the influence of z-pin reinforcement type on towards the tensile stress-strain behaviour of the butted double lap joints. For the unpinned joint, the stress-strain curve rises linearly to a peak in-plane tensile stress of 287 MPa with a minimal exhibition of a pseudo ductile strain of 0.011% ($\pm 0.004\%$) followed by ductility before final failure final fracture. The double lap joint failed along the co-cured bond-line interface, as shown in Fig. 4b. A 5% and 18% improvement in the ultimate tensile strength and strain-to-failure, respectively was observed-measured for the composite joints containing the copper and stainless steel z-pins, respectively. The z-pinned joints exhibited various failure modes. As observed in Fig. 5e, the copper z-pins failed under shear (Fig. 4c) whereas the stainless steel z-pins failed by underwent pull-out (demonstrated in Fig. 4b and 4d). Evidence of shear-induced necking was observed along the cross-sections of the two metal pin types.

The pseudo-ductile failure strain for the copper and steel z-pin reinforced joints was measured to be 0.112% ($\pm 0.012\%$) and 0.104% ($\pm 0.011\%$), respectively. The double lap joint containing the carbon fibre/BMI z-pins did exhibit an increase in the failure strength by 12% in comparison to the unpinned joint. However, no statistically significant improvement ($\sim 3\%$) in the failure strain was observed. The carbon fibre/BMI z-pins failed under shear, as shear, consistent with that reported in [11-13].

Previous studies on the Mode-II traction load have demonstrated that a grid of carbon z-pins exhibit higher shear strength yet lower strain to failure compared to stainless steel and copper z-pins under in-plane shear loading [11]. In comparison to the metal z-pins, the carbon z-pins are effective in transmitting high loads after bond-line crack which further inhibits delamination crack growth resulting in an increase in the higher failure stress strength. The metal pins are capable of carrying a greater load over a high shear strain [11, 13-15]. Also, the additional increase in the ultimate strength was due to the z-pins bridging the crack along the co-cured interfaces, thereby increasing the load required to propagate the delamination crack between the ply adherends [13-15]. The failure strain increases due to the metal z-pins bridging behind the crack front, which hence, plastically deformed over a large strain before shear induced rupture [11]. The bridging process of the metal pins further supplementing induces the pseudo-ductile strain response while retaining a stress of ~300 MPa over an axial strain of 0.11%. The toughening mechanisms induced by the metal z-pins can be analogous to the mineralized bridging that occurs in nacreous natural structures [7, 12, 16, 17]. These mechanisms, along with additional intrinsic and extrinsic toughening mechanism that operate at multiple length scale promote an enhanced strength and strain to failure simultaneously [7, 17].

Figure 4: (a) Stress-strain curve for composite double lap joints containing z-pin reinforcements. (b) Representative optical microscope images of the failure modes observed for unpinned and stainless steel z-pinned co-cured double lap joints. SEM fractography of double lap joints containing (c) copper z-pins and (d) stainless steel z-pins.

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4 CONCLUSIONS SUMMARY

Two different designs of platelet composites based on nacre-inspired design motifs, with the joints being fully aligned or staggered, have been investigated to characterise the effect of overlap length on strain ductility. The results show that both strength and ductility increase asymptotically with ply-overlap length. Computational models have been developed to capture the damage and delamination mechanisms. Staggering the ply gaps throughout the thickness of the discontinuous composites further enhances the ultimate tensile strength retention. Mimicking the extrinsic toughening mechanisms observed in nacre microstructures, through-the-thickness reinforcements, or z-pins, have been found to provide additional ductility enhancement. These new results suggest that through-thickness reinforcement using ductile z-pins offers a promising technique to engender platelet composites with a pseudo-ductility characteristic.

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REFERENCES

- [1] M.C.S. Moreno and J.L.M. Vincente, In-plane shear failure properties of a chopped glass-reinforced polyester by means of traction-compression biaxial testing, *Composite Structures*, **122**, 2015, pp. 440-444 (doi: [10.1016/j.compstruct.2014.12.018](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2014.12.018)).
- [2] H. Li, W.X. Wang and T. Matsubara, Multiscale damage progression in newly designed UACS laminates, *Composites Part A*, **57**, 2014, pp. 108-117 (doi: [10.1016/j.compositesa.2013.11.003](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2013.11.003)).
- [3] J.N. Baucom, J.P. Thomas, W.R. Poque and M.A.S. Qidwai, Tiled Composite Laminates, *Journal of Composite Materials*, **44**, 2010, pp. 3115-3132 (doi: [10.1177/0021998310373516](https://doi.org/10.1177/0021998310373516)).
- [4] J.D. Fuller and M.R. Wisnom, Exploration of the potential for pseudo-ductility in thin ply CFRP angle-ply laminates via an analytical method, *Composites Science and Technology*, **112**, 2015, pp. 8-15 (doi: [10.1016/j.compscitech.2015.02.019](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2015.02.019)).
- [5] G. Czel, M. Javaland and M.R. Wisnom, Demonstration of pseudo-ductility in unidirectional hybrid composites made of discontinuous carbon/epoxy and continuous glass/epoxy plies, *Composites Part A*, **72**, 2015, pp. 75-84 (doi: [10.1016/j.compositesa.2015.01.019](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2015.01.019)).
- [6] Y. Swolfs, Y. Meerten, P. Hine, I. Ward, I. Verpoest and L. Gorbatikh, Introducing ductility in hybrid carbon fibre/self-reinforced composites through control of the damage mechanisms, *Composite Structures*, **131**, 2015, pp. 259-265 (doi: [10.1016/j.compstruct.2015.04.069](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2015.04.069)).
- [7] U.G.K. Wegst, H. Bai, E. Saiz, A.P. Tomsia and R.O. Ritchie, Bioinspired structural materials, *Nature Materials*, **14**, 2014, pp. 23-36 (doi: [10.1038/nmat4089](https://doi.org/10.1038/nmat4089)).
- [8] J.G. Czel, S. Pimenta, M.R. Wisnom and P. Robinson, Demonstration of pseudo-ductility in unidirectional discontinuous carbon fibre/epoxy prepreg composites, *Composites Science and Technology*, **106**, 2015, pp. 110-119 (doi: [10.1016/j.compscitech.2014.10.022](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2014.10.022)).
- [9] K. Pingkarawat and A.P. Mouritz, Comparative study of metal and composite z-pins for delamination fracture and fatigue strengthening of composites, *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, **39**, 2016, pp. 180-190 (doi: [10.1016/j.engfracmech.2016.01.003](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engfracmech.2016.01.003)).
- [10] J. Ahamed, M. Joosten, P. Callus, S. John and C.H. Wang, Ply-interleaving technique for joining hybrid carbon/glass fibre composite materials, *Composites Part A*, **84**, 2016, pp. 134-146 (doi: [10.1016/j.compositesa.2016.01.010](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2016.01.010)).
- [11] F. Pegorin, K. Pingkarawat, S. Daynes and A.P. Mouritz, Mode II interlaminar fatigue properties of z-pinned carbon fibre reinforced epoxy composites, *Composites Part A*, **67**, 2014, pp. 8-15 (doi: [10.1016/j.compositesa.2014.08.008](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2014.08.008)).
- [12] D.V. Wilbrink, M. Utz, R.O. Ritchie and M.R. Begley, Scaling of strength and ductility in bioinspired brick and mortar composites, *Applied Physics Letters*, **97**, 2010, pp. 1-3 (doi: [10.1063/1.3499294](https://doi.org/10.1063/1.3499294)).
- [13] Pegorin, F. 2016: An experimental investigation of multi-functional z-pinned carbon-epoxy composites, PhD Thesis, RMIT University, 2016.

- [14] P. Chang, A.P. Mouritz and B.N. Cox, Properties and failure mechanisms of pinned composite lap joints in monotonic and cyclic tension, *Composites Science and Technology*, **39**, 2006, pp. 2383-2397 ([doi:10.1016/j.compscitech.2005.11.039](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2005.11.039)).
- [15] K. Pingkarawat and A.P. Mouritz, Comparative study of metal and composite z-pins for delamination fracture and fatigue strengthening of composites, *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, **154**, 2016, pp. 180-190 ([doi:10.1016/j.engfracmech.2016.01.003](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engfracmech.2016.01.003)).
- [16] G.X. Gu, F. Libonati, S. Wettermark and M.J. Buehler, Printing nature: unravelling the role of nacre's mineral bridges, *Journal of the Mechanical Behaviour of Biomedical Materials*, **InPress** (at the time of submission), 2017, ([doi:10.1016/j.jmbbm.2017.05.007](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmbbm.2017.05.007)).
- [17] R.K. Chintapalli, S. Bretonm A.K. Dastjerdi, F. Barthelat, Strain rate hardening: a hidden but critical mechanism for biological composites, *Acta Biomaterial*, **10**, 2014, pp. 5064-5073 ([doi: 10.1016/j.actbio.2014.08.027](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actbio.2014.08.027)).